

D1.1 - Data Management Plan (DMP) (Version 2 – updated on Month 24)

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Executive Summary

The aim of a Data Management Plan (DMP) is to plan the life cycle of data within the RESILEX project. It offers a long-term perspective by outlining how data will be generated, collected, documented, shared and preserved within the project.

1. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

1.1. Introduction

The aim of a Data Management Plan (DMP) is to plan the life cycle of data within the RESILEX project.

The introduction of novel or improved solutions (in terms of materials, processing technologies and business models) within the raw material production industry is often inhibited by limited access to the latest insights and state-of-the-art knowledge that would instead allow faster adaptation, innovation and technology transfer within the sector. This is particularly true for the critical raw material sector, given the strategic and economic importance for a company to master a process or product in order to keep a market share which sometimes implies a (quasi)-monopolistic situation. The choice of RESILEX to grant access to advanced analysis, open reports investigating cross-sectoral demonstration pilots and fully open policy and industrial recommendations will assist in avoiding lengthy and monopolistic processing experimentation and validation and will contribute to promoting a novel approach to quickly scale-up RESILEX innovations.

The 17 technical, professional and scientific publications that will be produced by our project will be open access in order to be compliant with the general principle of the Horizon Europe funding programmes. ISMC will clarify to all partners that embargo periods and article processing charges for hybrid open access publication are not allowed by Horizon Europe rule. This general rule is reinforced in section dedicated to Article 17 within Annex 5 of RESILEX Grant Agreement, which states that only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

To achieve a fully open research publishing model, ISMC will encourage partners to use Open Research Europe, which follows the F1000 model. When partners leading publications require journals with a listed impact factor, the open access compliance will be achieved by mainly targeting publishers that provide 'gold' access, either by making the articles immediately accessible online for free of charge publication, or by having each affiliated partner to cover the relevant cost.

Whenever the 'gold' access model cannot be applicable, we will take the benefits of the 'green' model instead, by supplementary publishing the relevant articles to an online repository, in consultation with the publisher. The OpenAIRE initiative is a good example of storing publications in the case of the 'green' model. We strongly believe that by giving open access to our scientific publications we will aim to speed up important breakthroughs by the European researchers that will lead to boost knowledge and competitiveness in Europe. In order to implement open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools from the very beginning of the project and throughout its full duration, open sciences practices will be structurally considered in task T1.4 of Project management., with the support of experienced partners in this field such as IMPERIAL and CEA in line with RESILEX project proposal and Grant Agreement. The collaboration of other partners will be sought, particularly academia profiles. Task T1.4 will also focus and capitalise on the role and synergies between partners' experiences, competencies, capabilities, and how partners will protect, share, manage IPR capital and actual exploitation. It will specifically include innovation, financing and replication management such as:

- Planning for open innovation and replication success, understanding and using innovation management techniques and processes during the lifetime of the project
- Identifying and fostering innovation and replication enablers/driving factors, especially at all levels (local, regional, national and European);
- Evaluating and improving the performance of the replication management system;
- Systematically capture structured data on project innovations, related to innovation readiness, innovation management, and market potential (both TRL – Technology Readiness Level, and MARL – Market Adoption Readiness Level);
- Identification and exploitation of positive spill overs.

In addition, external opportunities (from other projects, from networking activities, etc.) and internal opportunities (from partners) will be integrated into the project by the consortium if considered relevant.

Within this framework, this document offers a multi-layered perspective by outlining how data will be generated, collected, documented, shared, preserved and deleted within the project.

RESILEX DMP will be a non-restricted, public deliverable, under open access and a CC BY license to allow a broad re-use. This DMP will be made available as part of the deliverables on the EU CORDIS website and the updated versions will be shared via the Zenodo repository and Open Research Europe.

In order to align RESILEX's Data Management Plan, with the direction that the EU legal framework and EU authorities set, this document will base its grounding on the FAIR Data Management in Horizon Europe, which defines a Data Management Plan as a key element in ensuring that data is managed properly. To this end, it is necessary to identify the type of data that will be generated in the framework of the project, which includes:

- **Data generated from openly accessible information** such as reports on photovoltaics and related raw materials, statistics of the relevant application sectors, or other topics related to the objectives of the RESILEX project.
- **Data generated by partners of the project and external collaborators activities**, such as experimental, observational, images, text, numerical, and their estimated size; if applicable, combination with, and provenance of, existing data presented in the form of deliverables, technical documents, meetings minutes and other work carried out to achieve the objectives of the RESILEX project.

According to another classification, which does not exclude the previous one, there will be three types of data collected:

- Personal data, collected to facilitate the collaboration of the consortium and external partners (e.g. targeted stakeholders and collaborators)
- Technical data, collected e.g. in the context of test and validation activities
- Business-related data, collected in the context of innovation management and exploitation activities of the project partners.

1.2. Versions and Updates

The Data Management Plan (DMP) has been developed following the project plan. The document will be updated for the duration of the project as per the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management of Horizon Europe. Such updates will occur due to:

- Significant changes in the project such as the availability of essentially new data sources or changes due to the operations of pilot sites
- Changes in consortium policies
- Changes in consortium composition
- Any other reason that might be of relevance to the project

The DMP will be reviewed and revised as per the following timetable:

Version 1 :The first version of DMP takes into account the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), that is applicable since May 25th of 2018, and which introduce multiple changes with respect to the former legislation (i.e. Directive 95/46/EC) regarding ‘protection of the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons and in particular, their right to the protection of personal data’, and Directive 2002/58/EC on privacy and electronic communications; available on M6. EFUND contributes as reviewer.

Version 2 (current version) : The updated version of DMP was submitted at mid-term of the project; available on M24. EFUND contributes as reviewer .

Version 3 : The final version of DMP will be done before the end of the project in order to add information on how data will be administered once the project finishes; available on M48. EFUND will contribute as a reviewer. IMPERIAL as an expert in Open Science and CEA as WP7 leader will contribute to any revisions of v2 leading to v3.

1.3. Open Dissemination Strategy

The RESILEX Consortium will follow a proactive policy to disseminate the project results, with prior notice of any dissemination activity to all partners with sufficient information on the results to be disseminated.

To contribute to open sciences practices, RESILEX will grant:

- Immediate open access through a trusted repository (at the latest at the time of publication), therefore embargo on Open Access is not accepted;
- Publications licensed under CC BY (or equivalent); CC BY-NC/ND (or equivalent license prohibiting commercial use or derivative works) allowed for long-text formats;
- Provision of physical or digital access to data or other results needed for validation of conclusions scientific publications.

Since in consortium meetings, it was clear how some project participants struggled to understand the immediate Open Access rule, some tips and additional information are provided from Version 2 of this DMP. For instance, regarding the two ways to guarantee immediate Open Access.

1. Open Access Publishing:

Open Access journals offer anyone immediate open access to articles without a subscription. Some Open Access journals charge authors a fee to publish Open Access, the so-called Article Processing Charges (APC), and some don't (the so-called diamond open access journals). A list of qualitative, peer-reviewed Open Access Journals can be found in the Directory of Open Access Journals , DOAJ. Only APC costs in a fully Open Access journal or platform can be charged to the project. An APC to open 1 article in an otherwise non-open access journal, so-called Hybrid Open Access journals, will not be eligible. Researchers of European projects can also publish free of charge on the Open Research Europe platform. In any of these two cases, the publication must be uploaded and opened in a repository.

2. Deposit in an open repository: by depositing an accepted version of the publication in an institutional or subject repository you can immediately open a publication if the following condition is met:

- The author has transferred the copyright to the publisher who allows immediate open access to an accepted version uploaded in a repository.
- The author retains the copyright to the published article and can offer the publication themselves in Open Access. Sherpa/Romeo, the database giving an overview of copyright and open access (self-archiving) of publishers, can be accessed to check publisher policies.

Another key concept is embargo, which refers to a period during which access to your publication is restricted unless individuals pay for it through the publisher or have access through their institution's subscription. When you upload a digital copy of your publication to an online repository (Green OA), the publisher often enforces an embargo period. Typical embargo periods are 6 months for STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) and 12 months for HSS (humanities and social sciences). You can verify the specific embargo period required for a particular journal using Sherpa Romeo, which provides a journal-by-journal overview of publisher self-archiving policies.

Since embargo is not allowed by Horizon Europe rules, if your publisher imposes an embargo, there are still options to eliminate the embargo:

- Supplement your publisher's contract with an amendment
- Use the Rights Retention Strategy

The Rights Retention Strategy is grounded on the principle that the peer-reviewed Author Accepted manuscript is the intellectual creation of the authors and is their rightful property. Publishing in a subscription/hybrid journal that is not entirely Open Access may limit your ability to upload your publication to a repository without an embargo. By applying a CC BY license to your accepted manuscript, you retain copyright and can deposit a version in your open repository without paying any APCs. The goal of this strategy is to empower researchers to maintain sufficient intellectual ownership rights over their work. In order to use the Rights Retention Strategy, the following steps can be followed:

- Upon manuscript submission, include one of the following texts in the submission letter, on the first page, or in the acknowledgments:
- For EU (Horizon Europe) grants: "This work was funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe grant number 101058583. As set out in the Grant Agreement, beneficiaries must ensure that at the latest at the time of publication, open access is provided via a trusted repository to the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND, CC BY-NC-ND or equivalent licenses could be applied to long-text formats."

- Before signing a publisher's agreement, review the agreement for conflicts with your grant's open access requirement. Negotiate changes, request a waiver, or find a different open-access friendly journal if necessary. Do not sign something that obliges you to violate your grant agreement.
- When submitting your article, apply a Creative Commons CC BY license to your manuscript by including the text "CC BY 4.0" and/or the CC BY logo. This license allows for open access and enables you to deposit your work in an open repository without any article processing charges (APCs).
- Once your paper is accepted for publication, deposit your manuscript in a repository and ensure it's available by the time the official version is published.

1.4. Protection of Personal Data

Personal data collection will be limited in scope and will include the absolute minimum needed to establish the required collaboration among the project partners and external collaborators. All personal data will be securely stored.

All personal data will be processed according to the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data as well as Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

Overall RESILEX Ethic Protection of personal data

RESILEX will deal with ethics issues related to "Protection of Data" because collection of general data about companies (and potentially personal data from their employees) is needed to foster collaboration with other companies and projects as well as to perform some dissemination and communication activities.

Any data collected needs to comply with the European Regulation on Data Protection and Article 14 of the RESILEX Grant Agreement. So, external stakeholders or subcontractors participating in the different activities that would require data processing will be asked for their explicit consent on behalf of the project partnership explaining to them beforehand the purpose of the personal

data gathering, the processing method and any other legal obligation and rights around the personal data provided. The project team will use state-of-the-art technologies and current best practices for secure storage, delivery and access of personal information, as well as managing the rights of the users. In this way, there is a complete guarantee that the accessed, delivered, stored and transmitted content will be managed by the right persons, with well-defined rights, at the right time.

Corresponding procedures are being laid out at this DMP in addition to State-of-the-art firewalls, network security, encryption and authentication that will be used to protect collected data.

Firewalls prevent the connection to open network ports, and the exchange of data will be through -inter-alia- consortium known ports, protected via IP filtering, encrypted communication (SSL/TLS), or any other current, legal-compliant, best practice-used , encryption and password verification methods. Where possible (depending on the facilities of each partner) the data will be stored in a locked server, and all identification data will be stored separately.

Only authorised persons within authorised organizations will have access to all the users' identities. Only pseudonymised, or anonymised when possible, data will be made available to out-of-the-project researchers. If any identifiable data is required, access to it will be granted only after the verification of legal basis for sharing the personal data.

Access to any private generated project database will be granted with an authentication server that will restrict access depending on the user identity. Access to those databases will be also filtered on a user-based policy. A periodic change of password and a minimum password quality policy will be enforced to ensure the security of the system. EMDesk platform managed by EFUND will be used to store the data and follow up on the project advancement. The access to EMDesk is ensured via personalised invitation by the administrator and secured via ID and password including an option for Multi-Factor Authentication.

2. FAIR DATA STRATEGY

The RESILEX project will follow FAIR¹ guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship (mandatory for defined open data) that will be used all across the length of the project. As per the FAIR principles data should be:

1. Findable
2. Accessible
3. Interoperable
4. Reusable

Access to data will be kept as open as possible, but also as closed as necessary for commercial and exploitation purposes. Some key elements defined to ensure open access to data under this DMP are the following:

- **Types of data/research outputs:** 17 reports, 3 experimental prototypes and 1 Open platform for EU policy recommendations.
- **Findability of data/research outputs:** Use of Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for RESILEX publications, use of standardised metadata frameworks, use of ORCID researchers identifiers. Publication on Open Research Europe, encouraging partners to adhere to a fully open research publishing model.
- **Accessibility of data/research outputs:** Full open access will be provided to 30 out of 55 RESILEX deliverables. All these deliverables will be fully accessible to enable a broader impact on the project's results. The restricted deliverables will be **D1.2, D1.3, D1.4, D1.5, D1.6, D1.7, D1.8, D2.1, D2.2, D3.1, D3.2, D3.4, D3.5, D5.2, D5.5, D5.7, D5.8, D6.1, D6.2, D6.3, D6.4, D8.4, D8.5, D8.6** and **D8.9**. They will be registered as sensitives and their access will be limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement, in order to foster a future scale-up of the research outputs within the border of Europe, fully in line with one of the main objectives of the Destination: to increase autonomy in the key strategic sector (raw materials) for EU industrial ecosystems and avoid knowledge leakage to third-countries.
- **Interoperability of data/research outputs:** Open-source fonts such as Manrope, Open Sans or Gravitas will be used as much as possible for reports.

- **Reusability of data/research outputs:** Open datasets will be used when possible, for the project. The results of the project will be made available in order to facilitate reproducibility. An analysis of sensitive data will be performed in order to avoid unexpected data leakage issues.
- **Curation and storage/preservation of data:** ISMC will be responsible for the storage and preservation of data. Dr. Santiago Cuesta López will be in charge of quality assurance for all data processed during the project.

1.1. How will data be made Findable?

The data management plan supports the effective collection and integration of RESILEX project data. Project-internal storage, processing, and sharing of project data will mainly happen through the project's EMDesk collaborative platform, which is protected from unauthorised access and which the project coordinator, manages. Information and data related to WP8 will mainly be shared in a dedicated TEAMS account managed by Tenerrdis and supervised by the project coordinator and WP8 leader. The transfer of project information by email will be limited to a strict minimum. Public project data will be mainly shared through the project website, social media, community, other dissemination channels and open repositories (i.e. ZENODO). It will be ensured that public project data will not contain critical personal data or confidential information.

1.1.1. Data gathering

In order to ensure the best treatment of the data as possible, and as early as possible, the RESILEX project will define the collections of data (datasets) that will be used all over the project. At the time of the elaboration of this report, the process for datasets definition is still open since partners are expected to start sharing datasets after M6. Beyond that point, data will be regularly collected while the DMP will be updated at least in M24 and M48. To this end, and led by ISMC, the RESILEX partnership will regularly perform data audits to identify, collect and properly manage the RESILEX's generated datasets.

Purpose of data Collection

"e.g.:

- to facilitate the collaboration of the consortium and external partners,
- to test and for validation activities,
- for innovating management and exploitation activities of the project partners,
- to run an online community"

Relation to the Objectives of the project

"e.g.:

- Implementation of the digital data-driven pipeline for collaborative Product-Service Factories schema,
- Definition and development of hardware and software architecture that interconnects and makes interoperable the different manufacturing modules in the different manufacturing stages,
- Implementation of a methodology optimising the production planning from the large-part features"

Types and formats of data generated/collected

"e.g.:

- ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot, docx,
- Report, xlsx,
- Demonstrator,
- Personal data,
- Technical data,
- Business-related data,
- Other"

Reuse of existing data

"e.g.:<incidents of reusing - who, when, why>"

Origin of data

"e.g.:

- reports on modular production systems,
- statistics of the relevant application sectors,
- partners of the project,
- external evaluator activities"

Size of data

"e.g.: 5MB"

Data security

"e.g.:

- pseudonymisation,

- anonymization,
- encryption,
- limited access"

Archiving and preservation

"e.g.: retention of the data - 4 years since the end of the project"

Ethics (for personal data)

"e.g.:

- the data subject has some particular disability
- data subject is minor"

1.1.2 Data discoverability

Considering the FAIR data principles, public project data should be Findable by:

- Being assigned to a globally unique and persistent identifier
- Containing enough metadata to fully interpret the data, and
- Being indexed in a searchable source

By applying these principles data becomes Findable.

1.1.3. Data identification mechanisms

All documents associated with the project will be identified with a unique, and persistent, numeric identifier that will be given at the time of the submission process¹.

Examples:

Deliverables: RESILEX D1.1 M6 Data Management Plan v1.0 Final

- Project acronym
- Deliverable number
- Expected month of delivery
- Deliverable title
- (Vx.x for version number or Draft/Final - optional)

¹ Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship. Sci. Data 3:160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (2016).

Other documents: RESILEX WP6 EB meeting presentation

- Project acronym
- Work Package Number
- Object
- (Vx.x for version number and/or Draft/Final - optional)

1.1.4. Naming conventions

The project document naming conventions are as per the list below developed at the University of Edinburgh²:

1. Keep file names short, but meaningful
2. Avoid unnecessary repetition and redundancy in file names and file paths
3. Use capital letters to delimit words, not spaces or underscores
4. When including a number in a file name always give it as a two-digit number,
5. i.e. 01-99, unless it is a year or another number with more than two digits.
6. If using a date in the file name always state the date 'back to front', and use four-digit years, two-digit months and two-digit days: YYYYMMDD or YYYYMM or YYYY or YYYY-YYYY.
7. When including a personal name in a file name give the family name first followed by the initials.
8. Avoid using common words such as "draft" or "letter" at the start of file names, unless doing so will make it easier to retrieve the record.
9. Order the elements in a file name in the most appropriate way to retrieve the record.
10. The file names of records relating to recurring events should include the date and a description of the event, except where the inclusion of any of either of these elements would be incompatible with rule 2.

² Gryzbowski, A., University of Edinburgh: (July 2007). Naming Conventions for Electronic Records. Retrieved from <https://www.ed.ac.uk/records-management/guidance/records/practical-guidance/naming-conventions> on 4 June 2019.

The file names of correspondence should include the name of the correspondent, an indication of the subject, the date of the correspondence and whether it is incoming or outgoing correspondence, except where the inclusion of any of these elements would be incompatible with rule 2.

The file name of an email attachment should include the name of the correspondent, an indication of the subject, the date of the correspondence, “attach”, and an indication of the number of attachments sent with the covering email, except where the inclusion of any of these elements would be incompatible with rule 2.

The version number of a record should be indicated in its file name by the inclusion of “V” followed by the two-digit version number (x.x) and, where applicable, “Draft”. Avoid using non-alphanumeric characters in file names.

1.1.5. Document versioning

Only documents created by the consortium will be versioned. To this end, document templates include a history panel (see Table 1) for keeping track of the document versioning:

Table 1. Document template extract showing the history panel

Versio n	Date	Editors	Description
V0.1	26/02/2023	John Smith	Initial Draft
V1.0	18/03/2023	John Smith	Final Version

Project partners will identify different document versions by using a two-digit version number (Vx.x), optionally followed by the descriptor “Draft”. A document reviewed by another partner should be returned to the principal author by including the “*Edit+Initials*” of the secondary author(s)/editor(s). Only the principal author will change the draft number and will add the term Final to documents ready to be sent to the EU (or those to be used as final versions by the Consortium internally).

1.1.6. Metadata standards

Basic metadata will be used to facilitate the efficient recall and retrieval of information by project partners. Additionally, it will contribute to facilitating the discoverability of the requested information. To this end, all documents related to the project have to include, in the front-page, an information panel with information about the author(s) and contributor(s), WP, dissemination level, and nature of the document (when possible, otherwise this information will be included within the related dataset form to be provided by the dataset author(s)). Always it will be possible, RESILEX partnership will use official European Commission templates and tables to display this information in the most homogenized way. In the contrary case, the consortium will include a table to display that information. (E.g. See Table 2).

Table 2. Document template example showing the information panel on the front page

Project	RESiLEX – Resilient Enhancement for the Silicon Industry Leveraging the European matrix
Grant Agreement Number	101058583
Coordinator	Iberian Sustainable Mining Cluster (ISMC)
Work package N°	WPXX
Work package title	
Work package leader	
Document title	
Lead Beneficiary	
Dissemination level	
Authors	
Contributors	
Reviewer(s)	
Issue date	

The “Dissemination level” in the document information panel (see Table 2) has three possibilities:

- Public - PU
- Sensitive – SEN (limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement)
- EU classified - EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444

1.2. How will data be made accessible?

1.2.1. Which data will be made openly available?

Project data, materials (dissemination and communication) and deliverables that are declared as public will be pseudonymised (if needed) and made available to the public (through the project website, social media channels, community and/or open repositories. Furthermore, the pseudonymised data sets will be exploited through the creation of tables and infographics that may be used as part of the dissemination activities of the project.

Pseudonymisation is the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person (GDPR, art. 4(5))³.

1.2.2. How will data be accessed?

The data sets will be made available through the project website and/or through other specific-for-purpose channels such as the ZENODO open repository (or other partner’s regularly used repositories). When possible, data will be offered under

³ Pseudonymisation techniques and best practices Recommendations on shaping technology according to data protection and privacy provisions. European Union Agency for Cyber Security. NOVEMBER 2019 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/pseudonymisation-techniques-and-best-practices/at_download/fullReport#:~:text=Pseudonymisation%20is%20the%20processing%20of,and%20organisational%20measures%20to%20ensure

conditions that no specific software tools will be needed to access the data (otherwise, information about needed software will be provided and open source prioritized). The pseudonymised data sets will be saved and stored in DOC, PDF or XLS formats, when possible, to facilitate their exploitation (as well as guarantee their long-term accessibility).

Restricted and confidential data will not be stored/handled under openly accessible tools (i.e. website, community, etc) but under the private project EMDesk and/or partners' private servers. Specific authorization and access to this data from 3rd parties will be specifically discussed on a by-case basis and if finally approved, then limited access will be granted (temporarily, for specific uses, etc.). In cases of public emergency, immediate open access to all research outputs should be allowed, if requested by the granting authority.

1.3. How will data be made interoperable?

1.3.1. How will the interoperability of data be ascertained?

The project partners will make reasonable efforts towards storing all data in the appropriate format that will make data re-usable by external parties that might be interested in exploiting the data generated during the project. Indeed, when possible, the generated data will be compatible with the needs of specific end users as proposed by Pagano et al³⁴.

1.3.2. Language used

The by-default language will be English, and the vocabulary to be used will be the common one within research and manufacturing sectors, addressing the specific target audience of SMEs, larger companies and their ecosystems. Vocabulary will not constitute a barrier to data interoperability and reuse. A glossary has been set up and will be incremented as time goes on.

⁴ P. Pagano, L. Candela, D. Castelli, "Data Interoperability", *Data Science Journal*, vol. 12, pp. GRDI19-GRDI25, 2013. DOI: 10.2481/dsj.GRDI-004

1.4. How will be data reuse increased?

1.4.1. Use of data by third parties

Two data access pathways for third parties are envisaged:

- Firstly, during the project, two different cases:
- Open datasets, publications and information. This information is directly offered by openly accessible tools (website, own or 3rd party open repositories, etc.).
- Restricted (or even confidential) datasets, publications and/or information. This type of data had been categorized as restricted or confidential due their potential impact onto the partners exploitation strategies and, thus, special provisions need to be ensured. Third parties will be only allowed access to anonymised data sets on a case-by-case basis, after request and approval by affected partners (those involved in the generation of that data and/or being affected by the disclosure of the information regarding their exploitation rights). The provision of project data to other parties will depend on the use that third parties want to make of it, and the added value of sharing such data. The request and discussion with affected partner(s) will be performed under the action of the Executive Board when needed, always following the governance rules settled in RESILEX Consortium Agreement.
- Secondly, after the end of the project, relevant data generated will be ensured for five years through the channels where data had been available (project website, community, social media or repositories).

1.4.2. For how long will data be available for reuse?

The Consortium will maintain project data in a reusable state for as long as possible after the end of the project; an initial minimum availability period of five years is foreseen (this time may change depending on agreements among the project partners).

1.4.3. Data quality assurance

The project coordinator, Dr. Santiago Cuesta López, will be responsible for assuring the quality of the data by making sure that datasets follow the FAIR principles included in this plan, and that data is updated on a regular basis.

Personal data processing will be done in accordance with EU, national, and international laws concerning the “data quality” principles listed below⁵:

- Data processing is adequate, relevant and non-excessive
- Accurate and kept up-to-date
- Processed fairly and lawfully
- Processed in line with the rights of data subjects
- Processed in a secure manner
- Kept for no longer that necessary and for the sole purpose of the project

The data quality assurance process will be in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR).

1.5. Security of restricted or confidential data

Since EMDesk is the preferred option that the RESILEX consortium will use for gathering restricted or confidential data, it is necessary to offer a quick review on their security mechanisms. As for example, even if the RESILEX consortium will use this system to control data, they remain property of the RESILEX consortium. Below a brief resume of main features. To ensure the highest infrastructure security, EMDESK is hosted with the Open Telekom Cloud (OTC) – one of the most secure and modern cloud data centres in the world. OTC infrastructure is operated in Deutsche Telekom’s highly secure twin-core data centres in Magdeburg and Biere, Germany,

⁵ Wilms, G. Guide on Good Data Protection Practice in Research of the European University Institute. (March 2017). Retrieved from <http://www.eui.eu/Documents/ServicesAdmin/DeanOfStudies/ResearchEthics/Guide-Data-Protection-Research.pdf> on 4 June 2019.

as well as data backup. All services are strictly regulated and are regularly checked and certified by independent institutions, in order to meet the latest security and data protection requirements (TISAX, Trusted Cloud, ISO 14001, ISO 22301, ISO 9001, ISO 20000, ISO 27001, ISO 27017, ISO 27018, CSA Star Level 2, TÜV Trusted Cloud Service, TCDP version 1.0). For more information, visit: <https://open-telekom-cloud.com/en/security/data-centers>

How EMDesk will treat RESILEX's data

The production systems, the database and the network are physically and logically separated from the enterprise infrastructure. In addition, EMDesk separates customer accounts logically at the data layer. There are strict security policies for employees' access. Access to customer data is only a last resort option, strictly controlled and logged, technically and legally limited to a handful of employees to ensure appropriate customer support under strict confidentiality conditions and supervision of senior management. To connect to EMDesk production infrastructure, employees must use secure authentication that is identity-based and restricted based on employee role using a least-privilege approach. EMDesk employees are trained on data protection and legally obliged to non-disclosure. When evaluating access levels, the security workgroup takes into account employee experience levels, responsibilities, and internal risk assessments.

How EMDesk safeguards RESILEX's data

Each user in EMDesk has a unique account with a verified business email address. EMDesk forces users to set account passwords validated against password policies with high security criteria, including complexity, reuse, and expiration requirements. Passwords are hashed and salted in accordance with industry best practice. 2-Factor Authentication is available as an additional security measure to protect EMDesk accounts. User sessions and IP addresses are individually tracked and can be individually audited or revoked by their user. EMDesk has a maximum session duration configured.

Protected in transit and at rest

EMDesk protects all data in transit or at rest using industry standard Transport Layer Security (TLS) and AES encryption. AES encryption is used for the transmission of any customer data between EMDesk datacenter locations, as well as between EMDesk data centres and end user devices. User files uploaded to EMDESK servers

are automatically encrypted with AES 256 using per-file keys. These encryption keys are stored in a secure key vault, which is a separate database decoupled from the file storage layer.

3. PUBLIC FUNDING DISCLAIMER

All public documentation produced within the framework of the project will inform of the funding source by adding the following disclaimer and EU flag:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

In case of datasets, when possible, under the metadata provision also the funding acknowledge will be included. Otherwise, the public funding disclaimer will be included within the datasets forms, provided together with the datasets.

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